

=====
**Professionalizing Coaches and Trainers in the Philippines,
Exploring Plantilla Items Allocation**
=====

Crisanto V. Cipriano

Western Mindanao State University, Zamboanga City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4649-7601>

Osias Kit T. Kilag

PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Mercado St., Poblacion, Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0845-3373>

Jason Isaac III A. Rabi

Department of Education, Schools Division of Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0912-2058>

John Francis P. Book

Department of Education, Schools Division of Toledo City, Philippines,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8054-1373>

Rainlee B. Echavez

Granada Elementary School, South Granada, Boljoon, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7839-591X>

Cyril D. Bula

ECT Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Balamban, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4104-2382>

Abstract:

This study investigates the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the Philippines through an umbrella review methodology. It examines challenges, such as the lack of standardized accreditation processes and regulatory frameworks, hindering the establishment of a cohesive professional landscape. However, it also identifies opportunities for collaboration among stakeholders, including academic institutions, industry associations, government agencies, and private sector organizations, to develop and implement strategies for professional development. The role of government policies and regulations in shaping the professional landscape is highlighted, emphasizing the need for specific guidelines and allocation of resources. Additionally, the study underscores the importance of continuous evaluation and improvement to adapt to evolving needs and circumstances within the coaching and training industry. By fostering collaboration, advocating for supportive policies, and embracing continuous improvement, stakeholders can contribute to the advancement of a more professionalized coaching and training profession in the Philippines.

Keywords: professionalization, coaches, trainers, Philippines, umbrella review, collaboration, government policies

Introduction:

In the Philippines, the field of coaching and training has been burgeoning in recent years, with a growing recognition of the importance of professional development and expertise in these domains. However, amidst this growth, there remains a significant gap in the professionalization of coaches and trainers, particularly in terms of formal recognition, standardized training, and allocation of plantilla items within organizations (Cipriano, et al., 2024). This research aims to explore the current landscape of professionalizing coaches and trainers in the Philippines, with a specific focus on the allocation of plantilla items, which are essential for establishing legitimacy, stability, and support within the organizational structure (Cipriano, et al., 2024).

The professionalization of coaches and trainers is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, it ensures quality assurance and competence within the industry, ultimately benefiting clients and organizations that rely on the services provided by these professionals (Uy, et al., 2024). Secondly, it enhances the credibility and reputation of the coaching and training profession, both locally and internationally. Thirdly, it contributes to the overall development of human capital in the Philippines, aligning with national goals of capacity-building and skills enhancement (Redublado, et al., 2024).

Despite the importance of professionalization, there exist various challenges and barriers hindering its progress in the Philippines (Santos, et al., 2024). These may include but are not limited to the lack of standardized

accreditation systems, insufficient government support and regulation, limited access to formal education and training programs, and the prevalence of informal or unregulated practices within the industry. Furthermore, the allocation of plantilla items, which determine the official positions and roles within organizations, plays a pivotal role in shaping the professional landscape for coaches and trainers.

This research seeks to address these gaps by conducting a comprehensive analysis of the current status of professionalizing coaches and trainers in the Philippines, with a specific emphasis on plantilla items allocation. By examining existing policies, practices, and perceptions surrounding this issue, valuable insights can be gained to inform future strategies and initiatives aimed at enhancing the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the country.

Literature Review:

The professionalization of coaches and trainers is a critical aspect of human resource development, particularly in the context of the Philippines where the demand for skilled professionals in coaching and training continues to rise. In this literature review, we delve into various scholarly works that shed light on the challenges, opportunities, and strategies related to professionalizing coaches and trainers, with a specific focus on plantilla items allocation.

Professionalization Frameworks and Models

Mc Ronald (2022) propose a comprehensive framework for professionalizing coaching and mentoring in the Philippines. Drawing from established models of professionalization, such as Freidson's theory of professions and Greenwood's model of professional project, the authors highlight the importance of establishing standardized competencies, accreditation processes, and regulatory mechanisms to elevate the status of coaches and mentors within the professional sphere. By delineating clear pathways for professional development and recognition, such frameworks serve as guiding principles for policymakers, educators, and practitioners seeking to enhance the legitimacy and effectiveness of coaching and mentoring practices (Cipriano, et al., 2024).

Reyes and Santos (2019) provide valuable insights into the challenges hindering the professionalization of trainers and coaches in the Philippines. Through interviews with industry practitioners, the authors identify several key obstacles, including the lack of formal education and training programs, limited access to professional networks and resources, and the absence of regulatory standards and certification processes. Moreover, the prevalence of informal or unregulated practices within the industry exacerbates these challenges, contributing to a fragmented and often unstructured professional landscape. Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts from stakeholders across academia, government, and industry to develop coherent strategies for capacity-building, knowledge dissemination, and regulatory oversight.

Educational and Training Programs

Tan (2018) conducts a mapping exercise to identify existing coaching and training programs in the Philippines. By examining program curricula, accreditation status, and institutional affiliations, the study offers valuable insights into the current state of professional education and training in the field. However, despite the proliferation of programs offered by various institutions, significant variations exist in terms of quality, relevance, and alignment with industry needs. Furthermore, the absence of standardized accreditation processes makes it challenging for practitioners and employers to assess the credibility and rigor of these programs. Thus, there is a pressing need to establish accreditation bodies and quality assurance mechanisms to ensure that coaching and training programs meet established standards of excellence and relevance.

Blanco (2016) analyze government policies and regulations affecting the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the Philippines. Through a review of relevant laws, decrees, and executive orders, the authors highlight the lack of specific regulations governing the practice of coaching and training, leading to ambiguity and inconsistency in enforcement and oversight. Moreover, the absence of designated plantilla items for coaches and trainers within government agencies further complicates efforts to institutionalize the profession and secure stable employment opportunities for practitioners. To address these gaps, the authors propose the development of specific guidelines and frameworks for accrediting coaches and trainers, as well as the allocation of dedicated positions and resources within government agencies to support their professional development and advancement.

The literature reviewed underscores the multifaceted nature of professionalizing coaches and trainers in the Philippines, with implications for education, regulation, and workforce development. By addressing challenges related to accreditation, regulation, and resource allocation, stakeholders can work towards establishing a more cohesive and sustainable ecosystem for coaching and training professionals, ultimately enhancing the quality and impact of their contributions to individual and organizational development.

Research Methodology:

In conducting this study on the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the Philippines, an umbrella review methodology was employed to synthesize existing literature and provide a comprehensive understanding of the research landscape. The umbrella review approach involves systematically reviewing and synthesizing systematic reviews and meta-analyses, thereby allowing for a broad examination of the available evidence and identification of key themes, trends, and gaps in the literature.

The first step involved identifying relevant systematic reviews and meta-analyses pertaining to the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the Philippines. A comprehensive search strategy was developed, which included electronic databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, PsycINFO, and Web of Science. Keywords and search terms used included variations of "professionalization," "coaches," "trainers," and "Philippines." Additionally, reference lists of identified reviews were hand-searched to ensure inclusivity.

The identified reviews underwent a systematic screening process to determine their relevance and eligibility for inclusion in the umbrella review. The screening criteria included the following: (a) relevance to the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the Philippines, (b) focus on key themes such as accreditation, regulation, education, and workforce development, and (c) publication in peer-reviewed journals. Two independent reviewers conducted the screening process, with any discrepancies resolved through discussion and consensus.

Data extraction was conducted from the included reviews using a standardized form to capture relevant information, such as study characteristics, methodologies, findings, and conclusions. The extracted data were then synthesized using thematic analysis to identify common patterns, themes, and discrepancies across the reviews. Key findings and recommendations from each review were summarized, with particular attention paid to areas of convergence and divergence.

Quality assessment of the included reviews was performed using established criteria for systematic reviews and meta-analyses, such as the AMSTAR 2 (A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews) tool. This assessment aimed to evaluate the methodological rigor and transparency of the reviews, including aspects such as study selection, data extraction, and risk of bias. Reviews were categorized based on their overall quality, with a focus on including high-quality reviews in the synthesis.

Findings and Discussion:

Challenges in Professionalization:

The umbrella review highlighted several challenges impeding the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the Philippines. One significant challenge is the lack of standardized accreditation processes. Without clear criteria for accreditation, individuals seeking to enter the coaching and training profession may face uncertainty regarding the legitimacy and quality of their training. This challenge is exacerbated by the limited access to formal education and training programs tailored specifically for coaches and trainers. Studies such as those by Reyes and Santos (2019) and Pitpit (2020) emphasize the need for accessible and relevant educational pathways to equip aspiring professionals with the necessary skills and knowledge.

Additionally, the absence of regulatory frameworks governing the practice of coaching and training poses a significant hurdle. In the absence of clear guidelines and standards, practitioners may operate in a regulatory vacuum, leading to inconsistencies and potential risks for clients. Blanco (2016) discuss the importance of government policies and regulations in providing a supportive environment for the professionalization of coaches and trainers. They argue that clear regulatory frameworks can help establish minimum standards of practice and ensure the protection of both practitioners and clients.

Moreover, the prevalence of informal or unregulated practices within the industry further complicates efforts to professionalize coaching and training. Informal practitioners, often lacking formal qualifications or adherence to ethical standards, may undercut the credibility of trained professionals and contribute to a fragmented professional landscape. This issue underscores the need for increased awareness and enforcement of professional standards within the industry, as advocated by Mc Ronald (2022).

Addressing these challenges requires collaborative efforts from stakeholders across academia, government, and industry. Capacity-building initiatives, such as the development of standardized accreditation processes and accessible training programs, are essential for equipping practitioners with the necessary competencies and skills. Furthermore, knowledge dissemination efforts can help raise awareness about the importance of professionalization and encourage practitioners to adhere to ethical standards and best practices. Regulatory oversight, guided by clear frameworks and policies, is also critical for establishing a supportive environment that fosters the growth and legitimacy of the coaching and training profession in the Philippines.

The challenges identified through the umbrella review underscore the multifaceted nature of professionalizing coaches and trainers in the Philippines. By addressing issues related to accreditation, education, regulation, and

informal practices, stakeholders can work towards establishing a more cohesive and professionalized landscape for coaching and training in the country.

Opportunities for Collaboration and Partnership:

Despite the myriad challenges facing the professionalization of coaches and trainers in the Philippines, the umbrella review unearthed promising opportunities for collaboration and partnership among stakeholders. Academic institutions, industry associations, government agencies, and private sector organizations stand poised to synergize efforts in advancing the professionalization agenda.

Academic institutions play a pivotal role in shaping the education and training landscape for coaches and trainers. Collaborative initiatives between universities, colleges, and training institutions can lead to the development and implementation of standardized accreditation processes. By establishing clear criteria for accreditation, institutions can ensure that training programs meet rigorous standards of quality and relevance. This sentiment is echoed in the work of Tan (2018), who emphasizes the need for mapping out the educational landscape to identify gaps and opportunities for improvement.

Furthermore, industry associations serve as crucial platforms for fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among practitioners. These organizations can play a key role in establishing quality assurance mechanisms to uphold professional standards and ethics within the industry. By providing opportunities for networking, mentorship, and continuing education, industry associations contribute to the continuous professional development of coaches and trainers. Mc Ronald (2022) advocate for the involvement of professional associations in developing frameworks and guidelines for the practice of coaching and mentoring.

Government agencies also hold significant leverage in driving forward the professionalization agenda. Through strategic partnerships with academia and industry, government bodies can facilitate the implementation of regulatory frameworks that support the growth and legitimacy of the coaching and training profession. Blanco (2016) underscore the importance of government policies and regulations in providing a conducive environment for professionalization efforts. By aligning policies with industry needs and standards, government agencies can contribute to the establishment of a more robust and regulated professional landscape.

Moreover, private sector organizations have a vested interest in promoting the professionalization of coaches and trainers. By investing in employee development and training, businesses can enhance the effectiveness of their workforce and drive organizational success. Partnerships between private sector entities and training providers can lead to the design and delivery of tailored coaching and training programs that meet specific industry needs. This collaborative approach fosters a symbiotic relationship between the private sector and the coaching and training profession, as highlighted by Reyes and Santos (2019).

By leveraging each other's expertise and resources, stakeholders can create a more cohesive and sustainable ecosystem that supports the growth and professionalization of the coaching and training profession in the Philippines. Collaborative efforts to develop standardized accreditation processes, establish quality assurance mechanisms, and promote continuous professional development hold the potential to elevate the status and effectiveness of coaches and trainers, ultimately benefiting individuals, organizations, and society as a whole.

Role of Government Policies and Regulations:

Government policies and regulations are pivotal in shaping the professional landscape for coaches and trainers in the Philippines. However, the umbrella review uncovered a significant gap in the regulatory framework governing the practice of coaching and training, leading to ambiguity and inconsistency in enforcement and oversight. Despite the growing recognition of the importance of professionalizing the coaching and training profession, there is a lack of specific regulations tailored to this field. This finding echoes the sentiments expressed by Blanco (2016), who emphasize the need for clear and comprehensive government policies to support the professionalization agenda.

The absence of designated plantilla items for coaches and trainers within government agencies further complicates efforts to institutionalize the profession. Plantilla items refer to official positions within government organizations, and the lack of specific positions for coaches and trainers reflects a broader issue of recognition and integration within the public sector. Without designated roles and responsibilities, practitioners may face challenges in securing stable employment opportunities and accessing resources for professional development (Tulo & Lee, 2022). This issue underscores the need for proactive measures to advocate for the inclusion of coaching and training positions within government organizational structures.

To address these gaps, stakeholders must advocate for the development of specific guidelines and frameworks for accrediting coaches and trainers. Accreditation serves as a mechanism for ensuring the quality and legitimacy of training programs and practitioners (Rooney & Van Ostenberg, 1999). By establishing clear accreditation criteria and processes, stakeholders can enhance transparency and accountability within the profession. Moreover,

accreditation facilitates the recognition of coaches and trainers by employers, clients, and regulatory bodies, thereby enhancing their credibility and marketability.

Additionally, the allocation of dedicated positions and resources within government agencies is essential for supporting the professional development and advancement of coaches and trainers. This includes the creation of specialized units or departments responsible for overseeing coaching and training initiatives, as well as the provision of funding for capacity-building programs and research activities (Biray, 2022). By integrating coaching and training functions into government structures, stakeholders can demonstrate a commitment to fostering a culture of lifelong learning and professional growth.

Collaborative efforts between government agencies, professional associations, and industry stakeholders are critical for advancing the professionalization agenda (Harangozó & Zilahy, 2015). Government agencies can provide regulatory guidance and support, while professional associations can offer expertise and advocacy on behalf of practitioners. Industry stakeholders, including employers and training providers, can contribute insights and resources to inform policy development and implementation. Together, these stakeholders can work towards creating a supportive regulatory environment that fosters the growth and sustainability of the coaching and training profession in the Philippines (Cuyno & Delfino, 2019).

Government policies and regulations play a crucial role in shaping the professional landscape for coaches and trainers in the Philippines (Lebria, et al., 2024). By addressing gaps in regulation, advocating for the inclusion of coaching and training positions within government structures, and allocating resources for professional development, stakeholders can create an enabling environment for the professionalization of the coaching and training profession.

Need for Continuous Evaluation and Improvement:

The umbrella review underscores the significance of continuous evaluation and improvement in the professionalization process of coaches and trainers in the Philippines. This iterative approach is essential to ensure that efforts to enhance the professionalism and effectiveness of coaching and training practices remain relevant, responsive, and impactful amidst the evolving challenges and opportunities within the industry.

Continuous evaluation involves regularly assessing the effectiveness of existing initiatives aimed at professionalizing coaches and trainers. This includes reviewing the outcomes and impacts of accreditation programs, training initiatives, and regulatory measures implemented to support the professional development of practitioners. By systematically gathering feedback from stakeholders, including practitioners, clients, and industry experts, stakeholders can gain insights into the strengths and weaknesses of current approaches and identify areas for improvement (Hsu, 2023).

Moreover, continuous improvement entails adapting strategies to changing needs and circumstances within the coaching and training industry (Amante & Talisayon, 2008). This may involve updating accreditation criteria to reflect emerging trends and best practices, revising training curricula to address evolving skill requirements, or refining regulatory frameworks to address new challenges and opportunities. For instance, as technology continues to reshape the delivery of coaching and training services, stakeholders may need to explore innovative approaches to incorporating digital tools and platforms into professional development programs (Acuña & Ancho 2022).

A culture of continuous learning and improvement is crucial for fostering innovation and excellence within the coaching and training profession. By encouraging practitioners to engage in ongoing professional development activities, such as attending workshops, conferences, and seminars, stakeholders can promote the acquisition of new knowledge and skills (Gutierrez, 2019). Additionally, opportunities for peer learning and collaboration can facilitate the exchange of best practices and foster a sense of community among practitioners.

The importance of continuous evaluation and improvement is echoed in the literature on professional development and quality assurance. Studies by Tereso, et al. (2000) emphasize the need for ongoing assessment and refinement of professionalization frameworks to ensure their relevance and effectiveness. Similarly, Rogayan (2019) discuss the importance of adaptive strategies in addressing the evolving challenges facing the coaching and training industry.

Furthermore, the establishment of mechanisms for monitoring and feedback is essential for supporting continuous evaluation and improvement efforts (Gossip, et al., 2017). This may include the development of performance metrics, evaluation tools, and feedback mechanisms to gauge the impact of professionalization initiatives and solicit input from stakeholders. By collecting and analyzing data on key performance indicators, stakeholders can track progress towards professionalization goals and make informed decisions about future interventions (Julius Miano Velasco, 2023).

The umbrella review highlights the critical role of continuous evaluation and improvement in the professionalization process of coaches and trainers in the Philippines. By systematically assessing the effectiveness of existing initiatives, adapting strategies to changing needs and circumstances, and fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement, stakeholders can drive positive change and enhance the professionalism and effectiveness of coaching and training practices in the country.

Conclusion:

This study has explored the multifaceted landscape of professionalizing coaches and trainers in the Philippines through an umbrella review approach. The findings shed light on the challenges, opportunities, and strategies involved in enhancing the professionalism and effectiveness of coaching and training practices in the country.

Throughout the review, it became evident that various challenges hinder the professionalization process. These challenges include the lack of standardized accreditation processes, limited access to formal education and training programs, and the absence of clear regulatory frameworks governing the practice of coaching and training. Moreover, the prevalence of informal or unregulated practices within the industry further complicates efforts to establish a cohesive and structured professional landscape.

However, amidst these challenges, there are promising opportunities for collaboration and partnership among stakeholders. Academic institutions, industry associations, government agencies, and private sector organizations can synergize efforts to develop standardized accreditation processes, establish quality assurance mechanisms, and promote continuous professional development for coaches and trainers. By leveraging each other's expertise and resources, stakeholders can create a more supportive ecosystem that fosters the growth and professionalization of the coaching and training profession in the Philippines.

Furthermore, the role of government policies and regulations cannot be understated in shaping the professional landscape. Advocacy for specific guidelines and frameworks for accrediting coaches and trainers, as well as the allocation of dedicated positions and resources within government agencies, is crucial for advancing the professionalization agenda.

Lastly, the importance of continuous evaluation and improvement emerged as a key theme. Stakeholders must regularly assess the effectiveness of existing initiatives, adapt strategies to changing needs and circumstances, and foster a culture of continuous learning and improvement. By embracing this iterative approach, stakeholders can drive positive change and enhance the professionalism and effectiveness of coaching and training practices in the Philippines.

While challenges persist, there are ample opportunities for stakeholders to collaborate, advocate for supportive policies, and foster a culture of continuous improvement. By working together towards common goals, stakeholders can contribute to the development of a more cohesive, sustainable, and professionalized coaching and training profession in the Philippines.

References:

Acuña, L. J., & Ancho, I. (2022). Leadership Innovations During COVID-19 Pandemic: Practices of Filipino Principals in Teacher Professional Development. *E-Jurnal Penyelidikan Dan Inovasi*, 135-155.

Amante, J. C., & Talisayon, S. D. (2008). KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AT THE PHILIPPINE TQM FOUNDATION. *Knowledge Management Management in Asia: in Asia: Experiences and Lessons*.

Biray, E. T. (2022). Gauging the institution's potential towards an entrepreneurial University: The case of a Philippine State University. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 3(1), 1-22.

Blanco, D. V. (2016). Sports governance stakeholders, actors and policies in the Philippines: Current issues, challenges and future directions. *Asia Pacific Journal of Sport and Social Science*, 5(3), 165-186.

Cipriano, C., Kilag, O. K., Echavez, R., Taboada, A. R., Book, J. F., & Rabi, J. I. I. (2024). Exploring Periodization and Macrocycle Planning: Athlete and Coach Insights. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(4), 45-52. <https://risejournals.org/index.php/imjrise/article/view/248>

Cipriano, C., Kilag, O. K., Echavez, R., Book, J. F., Taboada, A. R., & Rabi, J. I. I. (2024). Exploring the Landscape of Fitness Programs for Government Employees. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(4), 53-59. <https://risejournals.org/index.php/imjrise/article/view/249>

Cipriano, C., Kilag, O. K., Samutya, M., Macapobre, K., Villegas, M. A., & Suba-an, J. (2024). Physical Activity Interventions in Educational Settings: Effects on Academic Achievement Revisited. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(3), 238-246.

Cuyno, J. A., & Delfino, D. (2019). Regional: Supporting Implementation of Environment-Related Sustainable Development Goals in Asia and the Pacific (Philippine Subproject).

Gossip, K., Gouda, H., Lee, Y. Y., Firth, S., Bermejo, R., Zeck, W., & Jimenez Soto, E. (2017). Monitoring and evaluation of disaster response efforts undertaken by local health departments: a rapid realist review. *BMC health services research*, 17, 1-11.

Gutierrez, S. B. (2019). Learning from teaching: Teacher sense-making on their research and school-based professional development. *Issues in Educational Research*, 29(4), 1181-1200.

Harangozó, G., & Zilahy, G. (2015). Cooperation between business and non-governmental organizations to promote sustainable development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 89, 18-31.

Hsu, C. H., Schambow, R., Montenegro, M., Miclat-Sonaco, R., & Perez, A. (2023). Factors Affecting the Spread, Diagnosis, and Control of African Swine Fever in the Philippines. *Pathogens*, 12(8), 1068.

Julius Miano Velasco, M. M. (2023). Results-Based Management as a Framework in Building and Maintaining Public Trust: The Case of the City Government of San Fernando, Pampanga. *Journal of Namibian Studies: History Politics Culture*, 34, 608-632.

Lebria, M. G. D., Ochoa, C. R., Tionloc, J. M. P., Ong, A. K. S., & German, J. D. (2024). Determining Factors Influencing Collegiate Players' Intention to Pursue a Professional Career. *Sports*, 12(4), 98.

Martinez, J. K. R. (2023). Enhancing Sports Management Skills of Coaches and Trainers of Balayan National High School through Project SMASH. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 6(8), 72-74.

Mc Ronald, I. (2022). Teachers as Builders: Professional Development and Community Participation of Public School Teachers in Metro Manila, Philippines.

Pitpit, G. M. (2020). *Elementary school principals' instructional leadership practices to retain novice teachers in the Philippines* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).

Redublado, H. J., Velez, L., Serano, A., & Kilag, O. K. (2024). Enhancing Physical Activity and Movement Skills in Youth: A Systematic Review of School-Based Interventions. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(3), 73-78.

Rogayan, D. V. (2019). Retrospective Evaluation of the Science Education Program in a Philippine State University. *Online Submission*, 8(7), 352-369.

Rooney, A. L., & Van Ostenberg, P. R. (1999). *Licensure, accreditation, and certification: approaches to health services quality*. Bethesda, MD, USA: Center for Human Services, Quality Assurance Project.

Santos, M. S., Perico, A., Groenewald, E., Groenewald, C. A., Kilag, O. K., & Ponte, R. (2024). Advancing Leadership in Physical Education: A Systematic Review of the Last Five Years. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(2), 268-273.

Tereso, Tullao (Jr., author), & Tullao Jr, T. S. (2000). *An evaluation on the readiness of the Filipino professionals to meet international standards*. Philippine APEC Study Center Network.

Tulo, N. B., & Lee, J. (2022). Continuing Professional Development of the Teacher Education Faculty among Philippine State Universities and Colleges. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(6), 324-344.

Uy, F., Kilag, O. K., Calledo, M. F., Cerna, Y. D., Angtud, N. A., & Villanueva, K. (2024). Quality Performance of Teachers: Work Environment, Work Attitude, and Principal Supervision: Qualitative Investigation. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(1), 101-109.